

How to teach programming online

Photo by Stepan Babanin on Unsplash

[Update: This is a non-active course and there are no plans to relaunch it at the moment, but you can reuse or edit any material that appears here.]

Objectives

To introduce techniques and good practices to design your programming courses and evaluate students.

During this online workshop:

- We will show you how to design your programming courses in an efficient and productive way.
- We will talk about the utility of peer-review and the importance of feedback. We will discuss how to implement these practices.

- We will present different types of evaluations. For example, fill-in the blanks, faded examples, etc.
- We will recap good programming practices and how to promote them among your students.
- We will present the Live Coding practice. We will see examples that will help you to recognize details to take into account.

During this workshop, we will illustrate the concepts using examples written in R and Python.

Intended public of this course

In order to take this workshop, we expect you to be proficient in some programming language that you teach or that you have/want to teach. In particular, in this course we focus on R and Python.

When we designed this workshop, we had in mind Aurora, Patricio, and René as our learner personas.

- Aurora is a university professor. She doesn't have formal training in programming but has to teach programming concepts for her courses.
- Patricio has been a professional Python developer for 15 years. This year he will start to deliver training courses for his company. Besides, he teaches programming at a private academy.
- René learned many years ago a programming language that uses everyday for her data analysis job. recently, she had to learn R in order to start teaching courses because all the courses in the institution where she works switched to R.

Check out [personas](#) to read more about them.

Not included in this workshop

This is NOT a programming course (this is a course about how to teach programming). Since we only have 3 hours, a lot of things will be out of reach of the workshop. Among other things, we will not learn:

- Programming techniques

- Theory of pedagogy

Duration

This is a 3-hour workshop with intervals (ideally away from any screen) of approximately 5 minutes for every 50 minutes of content.

Sample schedule

Duration (min)	Activity
5	Time to connect and make sure your audio and video connection is good (if you don't have a camera it doesn't matter, but if you do, it helps)
15	Introduction to the course
30	Course design
20	Peer review & Feedback
25	Type of evaluations
15	Promote good programming practices
10	Teach to get help
30	Live Coding

Course materials

- [Presentation used during the course](#)
- [End-of-workshop feedback form template](#)

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